

DISCRETE DAMAGE MODELING IN LAMINATED COMPOSITES UNDER FATIGUE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

The Discrete Damage Modeling (DDM) method is extended for progressive failure analysis in laminated composites under fatigue loading. The essence of this technique is the insertion of true displacement discontinuities independent of mesh orientation to simulate matrix cracking. Multiple cracking in each ply is allowed. All plies are tied together by using cohesive interfaces, which are allowed to delaminate. Matrix cracks in two adjacent plies interact through the interface cohesive model, and their presence is a major delamination initiator. Failure criterion and cohesive zone model for initiation and propagation of cracking and delamination under fatigue loading were proposed. A material history variable in each integration point is introduced and updated after each loading increment, corresponding to certain load amplitude and the number of cycles. The computation begins without any matrix cracks present. A matrix crack is inserted when the material history variable value reaches unity. Delamination and matrix cracking extent under fatigue loading in open hole graphite epoxy laminates was predicted and showed good comparison with experiment.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fatigue properties of carbon fiber composites were studied intensively in the past and satisfactorily described for most isolated damage modes. The transverse strength properties have been shown to satisfy exponential S-N behavior, and the fracture related damage modes, such as delamination, have been shown to follow the Paris law. The delamination onset and propagation investigation in composite laminates has been a critical research topic for several decades, and is the subject of many reviews, e.g. [1-3]. Significant achievements in practical application of the virtual crack closure technique VCCT [4] to delamination propagation in laminated composite panels both in static and fatigue regimes were recently reported by Deobald and co-authors [5]. Although the delamination failure mode is of great practical importance, it cannot be considered in isolation from other less critical damage modes, e.g. matrix cracking [6]. Depending upon the layup and loading profile, the delamination propagation can be precipitated by matrix crack formation, which can drastically affect its propagation. Several scenarios directly influencing the damage tolerance assessment are possible: matrix cracking can temporarily arrest the delamination; it can divert the

delamination to a different interface; it may cause an avalanche of multiple delaminations through the thickness of the part.

Availability and rapid increase of computer power has enabled recent successes in the development of the Discrete Damage Modeling (DDM) technique, which is based on the direct simulation of displacement discontinuities associated with individual instances of matrix cracking occurring inside the composite plies, and delaminations at the interfaces between the plies. These methods employ variants of eXtended Finite Element Methodology (X-FEM) [7] and its regularized implementation (Rx-FEM) [8-11] in particular. The goal of the present work is to extend these methods for simulation of fatigue loading and experimentally verify the accuracy of the predictive techniques.

The Rx-FEM allows modeling the displacement discontinuity associated with individual matrix cracks in individual plies of a composite without regard to mesh orientation by inserting additional degrees of freedom in the process of the simulation. The propagation of the mesh independent crack is then performed by using the cohesive zone method. The kinematic aspect of the technique does not require any modification for fatigue loading, however the constitutive components do. There are two components of DDM framework, which require modification: the failure criterion for crack insertion and the cohesive law for damage initiation and propagation. It is these developments which will be discussed in detail in the present paper, whereas the Rx-FEM formulation details can be found in references [8-11]. The conceptual difficulty of application of cohesive zone models (CZM) in fatigue lies in different representation of the crack tip in such models as compared to classical crack tip representation, which is used in definition of the Paris law. This difficulty was recently addressed by Harper and Hallett [12]. It was shown how to extract the fracture mechanics point crack tip energy release rate (ERR) from the cohesive zone model, and subsequently directly apply the Paris law for cohesive crack propagation. In the present work, we further develop this concept by introducing the interpolation procedure for ERR calculation in the cohesive zone model, thus allowing the use of coarser meshes for analysis. We also complete the fatigue cohesive zone framework by combining the S-N information for the initiation phase with Paris law for the propagation phase for cracking and delamination. The proposed fatigue CZM makes no explicit or implicit assumptions regarding initial crack size for fatigue analysis, thus extending this key feature of CZM from static to fatigue. The final development required for completing the DDM fatigue framework is the new crack insertion identification law, which in static regime is performed by using the LaRC04 criterion [13]. We use Palmgren-Miner's rule to develop generic crack insertion methodology for fatigue loading regime. The propagation of the mesh independent crack is then performed by using the cohesive zone method. We will begin by describing the static and fatigue solution algorithms and fatigue extension of the failure criteria and cohesive zone formulation.

2 COMPUTATIONAL METHODOLOGY

2.1 Static Fracture Analysis

The DDM approach consists of Mesh-independent Crack (MIC) Modeling of transverse cracks in each ply of the laminate, and modeling the delamination between the plies by using a cohesive formulation at the ply interface. The matrix cracks are modeled by using the regularized formulation [8-11], termed Rx-FEM. The regularized formulation deals with continuous enrichment functions, and replaces the Heaviside step function with continuous function changing from 0 to 1 over a narrow volume of the so called gradient zone. The formalism tying the volume integrals in the gradient zone to surface integrals in the limit of mesh refinement was discussed in [9]. The simulation begins without any initial matrix cracks, which then are inserted based on a failure criterion during the simulation. The LaRC04 [13] failure criterion is chosen in the present work. The propagation of each MIC is performed by using the cohesive zone formulation [14]. Note that the delamination between the plies is simulated by using the same cohesive zone formulation; however, the cohesive element

between the interfaces is inserted during the initial model preparation. The schematic of the process is shown in Figure 1. After the failure criterion is met at a certain location, an MIC

Figure 1: Static Solution Algorithm

is added by using Rx-FEM. Next, the load is increased and the program enters a nonlinear iteration step at which the inserted crack(s) and/or delaminations are being opened. After convergence is achieved, the failure criterion is checked again for new crack insertion. This process can be coupled with progressive simulation of fiber failure and/or fiber criterion, if applicable. In the present paper, we will not consider fiber failure modes.

2.2 Fatigue Crack Insertion Criterion

Conceptually, the extension of the DDM framework shown in Figure 1 to fatigue loading is relatively straight forward. Indeed, the kinematic aspects of the DDM framework in terms of MIC insertion and delamination modeling remain unchanged, what requires development is the constitutive modeling of MIC and delamination opening, as well as crack insertion. In the present paper, we are developing ply level phenomenological framework for modeling fatigue response. Namely, we will use the S-N curves for ply level strength properties for modeling the damage initiation phase, and Paris law for modeling the growth of damage. Extension of the cohesive zone model to fatigue regime will be addressed in the subsequent section. In the present section, we will consider the fatigue failure criterion.

The fatigue failure criterion is built upon 3D static failure criterion LaRC04 described in [13]. The idea of constructing a fatigue failure criterion based upon a static criterion is due to Hashin and Rotem [18]. For a given frequency ϖ and $R=\sigma_{\min}/\sigma_{\max}$ ratio, the fatigue failure load σ is defined as the failure load amplitude vs. number of cycles to failure and can be expressed as

$$\sigma = \sigma^s f(R, N, \varpi) \quad (1)$$

where σ^s is the static strength and $f(R, N, \varpi)$ is the material fatigue function. In the present case, we only consider matrix failure modes and limit ourselves to the tension shear envelope. The idea expressed and experimentally verified in [18] consists of applying static failure criterion with degraded ply level strength properties, which are given by two S-N curves, namely normal tension $y(R, N, \varpi)$ and shear $s(R, N, \varpi)$, such that

$$Y(N)/Y_t = 1 - s_1 \text{Log}(N) \quad \text{and} \quad S(N)/S = 1 - s_2 \text{Log}(N) \quad (2)$$

where $Y(N)$ and $S(N)$ are reduced strength values as the number of cycles for transverse normal and shear strength, and Y_t and S are their static values respectively; s_1 and s_2 are material parameters. According to [18], the fatigue strength can be predicted by applying static failure criterion with the respective ply level strength values provided by the S-N curves (2). Two modifications are required to the methodology [18] for application in the DDM framework. First, we need to employ a 3D failure criterion capable of predicting the transverse cracking angle relative to the normal direction to the ply interface. Second, due to constantly changing loading amplitude during progressive damage simulation, we need to generalize the approach to variable amplitude loading. To address the first requirement, we employ the LaRC04 criterion [13]. In the tension-shear quadrant, it represents a quadratic criterion similar to [18]; however, it is applied to the so-called failure plane where the failure index attains its maximum value. In a 2D case, this plane is perpendicular to a ply midsurface; however, in the presence of transverse shear stresses, it can form at an angle to the ply interface. The second step required to complete the fatigue failure criterion development for DDM is generalization to variable amplitude loading. It is accomplished by applying the Palmgren-Miner linear damage accumulation hypothesis. For implementation purposes, we define a material point loading history parameter d_l as

$$d_l^q = \sum_{k=1}^q \frac{\Delta N_m^q}{N_f^k} \quad (3)$$

where summation is carried out over all previous load steps $1 \dots q$ and N_f^k is the limited number of cycles the specimen can survive within a given block of loading alone. The failure, according to the Palmgren-Miner hypothesis, occurs when d_l attains a value between 0.7 and 2.2 depending on the material, R , and loading frequency. Without restricting generality, we will assume that fatigue failure corresponds to $d_l = 1$. Based on this hypothesis and Eqn. (3), we can compute the number of cycles until the failure event ($d_l = 1$), which in our context corresponds to the insertion of an MIC as

$$\Delta N_c = \min_x \left[(1 - d_l^q) / N_f^{q+1} \right], \quad (4)$$

2.3 Fatigue Cohesive Law

As seen in the previous section, the extension of static failure criterion in the tension-shear quadrant for matrix failure mode to fatigue is conceptually transparent. A significantly more complicated situation arises with the cohesive zone models. Based on previous work [12, 15-17]; two problem areas can be identified. One area is simulation of the propagation of existing delamination according to Paris law. The difficulty here is that Paris law is defined within the classical fracture mechanics framework and uses the ERR or stress intensity factor magnitude associated with ideal crack tip singularity. On the other hand, the cohesive zone model introduces a process zone concept instead of the ideal crack tip. Two different approaches have been proposed to address this issue. One is based on explicitly bringing in the process zone length into the propagation mechanism, as described in [17]. The other approach proposed in Ref. [12, 15] extracts the ERR value of the classical crack tip from the process zone information, and uses it to propagate a fatigue crack similar to VCCT. In the present work, we will use the second approach for the delamination propagation phase. The second problem area of the cohesive zone model extension to fatigue analysis is the damage initiation phase and its transition into the propagation phase. It is this feature of the cohesive zone method, which has earned its popularity in static analysis. Consider bi-linear static cohesive law shown in Figure 2 with a dashed line. In the process of static deformation, material points move along the traction displacement jump curve in a continuous fashion from left to right assuring the transition from undamaged to damaged portion, and eventually to the fully separated state under load or stored energy. In fatigue regime, the situation is completely different in both the initiation and propagation regime in that the material points do not follow continuously the static cohesive traction law through the

initiation and propagation phases, and in some situations are not even located on the static cohesive law curve at all.

First consider the initiation stage and a material point A on the ascending portion of the cohesive law (see Figure 2). The point A has a ratio of stress amplitude to the static strength of approximately 0.5. According to S-N curves (2) this point will fail after $\Delta N_f = \exp(0.5/s_f)$ cycles, assuming that it was loaded in Mode I. However, what does it mean in terms of cohesive law? In [12] it is proposed to assign to this element the propagation damage variable of $d=1$ moving it all the way to the fully separated condition. The rationale behind it is that we will form a highly loaded crack tip zone, which will be in the propagation regime and can be treated by the VCCT like approach. This damage initiation approach is, however, similar to assuming a certain size of initial flaw, and that this size is also tied to the mesh density. We propose instead to modify the cohesive law in each point depending upon the history of how the damage initiation (DI) condition was achieved. Namely, we propose to reduce the initiation strength of the cohesive law to that at which the DI condition was reached under cyclic loading while maintaining the critical energy release rate (ERR) value for static propagation G_c . It is illustrated in Figure 2 where a new cohesive law for point A is shown with a solid line after the initiation variable $d_I = 1$. We change the slope of the cohesive zone model to maintain the static propagation characteristics. According to this hypothesis, each material point may have its own cohesive law. The proposed approach eliminates any ambiguity or need for initial damage size or presence of any cracks or delaminations in the structure.

Figure 2: Schematics of a cohesive zone model for static and fatigue simulation

To keep track of the loading history of each material point before crack insertion and after crack insertion, we use the damage history variable d_I and equation (4).

After the condition $d_I=1$ is achieved, the material point A appears at the onset of the propagation stage due to modification of the cohesive law. As mentioned previously, we will use the approach by Harper and Hallett [12], where the cohesive law is used to extract the value of ERR, and subsequently propagate the damage in a way similar to VCCT. In the propagation regime, the modified Paris law

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C \left(\frac{G_{\max}}{G_c} \right)^m \quad (5)$$

is used where G_c is the static critical value of the ERR, G_{max} is the maximum value of ERR during the cycle, and C and m are material fatigue constants. Analogous to VCCT, the crack is propagated one element at a time so that the number of cycles ΔN_p for propagation is

$$\Delta N_p = \frac{l_e}{C \left(\frac{G_{max}}{G_c} \right)^m} \quad (6)$$

where the length value for crack extension l_e is equal to one element size.

2.4 Fatigue DDM Algorithm

Two types of algorithms can be envisioned for modeling progressive failure in fatigue:

- (i) *Cycle based algorithm (CBA)*. In this algorithm, one predefines a number of fatigue cycles on each solution step and simulates the damage which occurs during this cycles
- (ii) *Event based algorithm (EBA)*. In this algorithm, one defines an increment of damage or damage event, such as new crack insertion or delamination extension for one element, and computes the number of cycles required to advance to this event.

Recapturing the notations for various initiation and propagation events:

- ΔN_c - insertion of new crack,
- ΔN_I - initiation of CZM damage progression (CZM modification),
- ΔN_p - CZM damage propagation of one interval,
- ΔN_{max} - specified maximum number of cycles per increment,

one can write down the number of cycles for each increment ΔN for an EBA as

$$\Delta N = \min(\Delta N_c, \Delta N_I, \Delta N_p, \Delta N_{max})$$

In a complex simulation, such as DDM, a combination of CBA and EBA is employed. Namely, the propagation events determine the number of cycles per increment, and the history variables for initiation events are updated according to this number of cycles, i.e

$$\Delta N = \min(\Delta N_p, \Delta N_{max})$$

and d_I – updated for the number of cycles ΔN .

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A [60/0/-60]_{3s} IM7/977-3 composite laminate with a 6.35mm central open hole was subjected to fatigue loading at 80% static failure load amplitude under tension-tension fatigue at R=0.1. IM7/977-3 ply level material properties and testing procedures were outlined in [21]. The DDM methodology uses standard ply level stiffness and strength properties measured by using ASTM standard methods. Static properties used in the simulations are shown in Table 1. In addition to these properties, the methodology requires fatigue S-N parameters s_1 and s_2 for normal and shear strength defined in Eqn.(2), as well as m and C parameters for Paris law defined in Eqn. (5) for Mode I and Mode II propagation. These properties are given in Table 2.

Material Property	Value
E_{11} (GPa)	164.0
E_{22}, E_{33} (GPa)	8.977
G_{12}, G_{13} (GPa)	5.02
G_{23} (GPa)	3.00
ν_{12}, ν_{13}	0.32
ν_{23}	0.496
α_1	0.00
α_2 (1/°C)	3.00e-05
G_{IC} (N/mm)	0.256
G_{IIC} (N/mm)	0.649
Y_T (MPa)	100.0
Y_C (MPa)	247.0
S (MPa)	100.0
X_T (Gpa)	2.9
X_C (Gpa)	1.27

Table 1: Static IM7/977-3 ply properties

Material Property	Value
S_1	0.03
S_2	0.075
m_1	7.32
m_2	6.354
C_1 (mm)	0.025
C_2 (mm)	0.065

Table 2: Fatigue IM7/977-3 ply properties

The [60/0-60]_{3s} laminate was fatigued for 200,000 cycles and subject to X-Ray CT inspection. Figure 3 displays the delamination pattern on each interface starting from the laminate top surface from left to right. Note that the

Figure 3: Delamination extent in $[60/0-60]_{3s}$ laminate after 200,000 cycles.

CT images on each interface contain some bleed through shading from neighboring interfaces. In order to evaluate the delamination patterns in detail, 3 interfaces were selected and are displayed in Figures 4-6 in an enlarged format. As seen in these figures, the delamination extent and distribution predicted by using DDM is in good agreement with the experimentally observed delamination patterns.

Figure 4: Delamination extent on 60/0 interface after 200,000 cycles. Matrix cracks- red, delamination- blue.

Figure 5: Delamination extent on outer 0/-60 interface after 200,000 cycles. Matrix cracks- red, delamination- blue.

Figure 6: Delamination extent on inner 0/-60 interface after 200,000 cycles. Matrix cracks- red, delamination- blue.

4 CONCLUSIONS

DDM methodology has been extended to fatigue loading. A combination of cycle and event based progressive damage modelling algorithms has been implemented. The cohesive zone based fatigue algorithm has been proposed, which eliminates any ambiguity or need for initial damage size or presence of any cracks or delaminations in the structure.

A $[60/0/-60]_{3s}$ open hole IM7/977-3 laminate fatigued at 80% static failure load with $R=0.1$ for 200,000 cycles was subject to X-Ray CT examination and displayed a good correlation of matrix cracking and delamination extent with DDM predictions on all interfaces.

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